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Altering Ecosystem Services While Considering Soil Health and Farm Income: Conceptual Framework in Crop Farming Systems

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ABSTRACT

As global interest in sustainable agriculture grows, there is increasing demand for improved supply of ecosystem services (ESs) from agroecosystems. To meet this demand, farmers must implement changes in production management. However, such changes not only alter ESs supply, they also affect two fundamental aspects of farming: soil health and farm income. Therefore, to support decision-making toward improved ESs supply, it is necessary to find out how altering ESs supply simultaneously affects soil health and farm income through production management changes. Several studies have looked at fragments of the problem. However, few consider ESs at the centre of the decision-making process or a broad range of ESs in an integrated way. To fill this gap, this paper presents a conceptual framework that aims to provide a first qualitative understanding to the question and a blueprint for further quantitative analysis. The framework sets “Altering ESs” as the central objective, and considers soil health, production management, and farm income as being influenced by this objective. From this approach, it appears that “Altering ESs” results in a sequence of requirements and consequences that together affect farm income. This sequence is described with four relations: (1) “Altering ESs” requires changes in production management, (2) such change can affect soil health, (3) “Altering ESs” indirectly influences soil health through production management, (4) and finally “Altering ESs”, production management, and soil health have a combined effect on farm income. Each relation is explored qualitatively based on existing literature. The findings offer valuable insights that can contribute to develop sustainable farm business models according to the “3P-concept” in which we consider ESs for People, soil health for Planet, and farm income for Profit. The framework highlights the potential for both synergies and trade-offs between ESs, soil health, and farm income, depending on a farmer’s context and decisions. Finally, the framework can serve as a blueprint for integrating ESs into bio-economic farm models.

1 | Introduction

Agriculture is the major human land use type (Robertson and Swinton 2005), and plays a key role in human society through its major positive and negative contributions to ecosystem services

(ESs), which are the “benefits people obtain from ecosystems” (MEA 2005). ESs include provisioning services, of food for example, as well as regulating, supporting, and cultural services such as pollination and climate regulation (MEA 2005). They are crucial for human survival (Kremen 2005) and well-being

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Summary

- It is unclear how altering ecosystem services (ESs) supply affects soil health and farm income.
- This is the first concept bridging ESs supply, soil health, and farm income holistically.
- Altering ESs supply leads to various synergies and trade-offs with soil health and farm income.
- The proposed framework can serve as a blueprint for deeper quantitative analysis.

(Costanza et al. 1997; McMichael et al. 2005; MEA 2005; TEEB 2010), and for tackling sustainable development challenges as outlined in the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Wood et al. 2018; Xu and Peng 2024). ESs are also vital to farmers' livelihood, as provisioning ESs represent a main income source, and other ESs support resilience (DeClerck et al. 2016) and long-term productivity (Robertson and Swinton 2005). But, while agriculture has largely contributed to food provisioning (Zhang et al. 2007), it has also substantially degraded other ESs (DeClerck et al. 2016; MEA 2005; Robertson and Swinton 2005). As a result, various societal actors are now demanding farmers to alter ESs supply (Arla Foods, n.d.; European Commission 2021; Perrot-Maitre 2006; Schulte et al. 2019), which in this paper refers to improving at least one ES other than food provisioning, while potentially affecting the supply of other ESs.

To alter ESs supply, farmers must change their production management and decide which specific changes to implement. Production management is defined as the set of decisions that can be made by a farmer in a crop production system in terms of land use activities, crop management, and soil management (adapted from Kik et al. 2021). While farmers have numerous options for modifying production management, it is important for them to decide which specific changes to implement, as each change may affect ESs differently. For instance, agroforestry tends to increase biodiversity, water quality, carbon sequestration (Beillouin et al. 2021), and aesthetics (Smith et al. 2013), while decreasing fertilizer rate can increase water quality (Di and Cameron 2002; Drinkwater and Snapp 2007; Quemada et al. 2013) but might reduce harvested crop production (Gardner and Drinkwater 2009; Quemada et al. 2013; Van Ruyambeke et al. 2023).

While it is important to decide which production management changes to implement when aiming to alter ESs supply, other farm-related aspects must also be integrated in the decision-making process. This is because such changes might simultaneously affect other farm aspects that are crucial for ensuring long-term improvement in ESs supply and actual adoption of changes by farmers. In particular, it is important to consider how altering ESs supply simultaneously affects soil health, defined as the "continued capacity of soils to support ecosystem services" (European Commission 2020). This is because soil health is key for the long-term soil ESs supply (Drobnik et al. 2018), but has been largely degraded worldwide (FAO and ITPS 2015). In addition, it is important to consider how altering ESs supply affects farm income as changes beneficial for ESs supply can incur farm

income losses (Swinton et al. 2007), which in turn could impede farmers' decision to adopt those changes (Dominati et al. 2019). This is partly because most ESs, as well as soil health, are not yet economically valued in the market. Still, many ESs are potentially marketable and, when marketed, could become a lever to incentivize farmers to alter ESs supply.

To support farmers' decision-making to alter ESs supply while integrating soil health and farm income in decision-making, it is crucial to find out how altering ESs supply simultaneously affects soil health and farm income through production management changes. Several studies have addressed part of this question by linking some of its four elements: ESs, soil health, farm income, and production management. Current literature extensively addresses the impact of production management changes on ESs supply and soil health (e.g., Bai et al. 2018; Beillouin et al. 2021; Cozim-Melges et al. 2024; Sandén et al. 2018; Tamburini et al. 2020), and the direct link between soil (health) and soil ESs (Adhikari and Hartemink 2016; Dominati et al. 2010; Drobnik et al. 2018; Schwilch et al. 2016). In addition, in the context of an assessment framework for sustainable bioeconomy, Helming et al. (2018) linked soil, soil ESs, and production management. In parallel, Stevens (2018) incorporated soil health, farm management, and farm income within one framework. More recently, Kik et al. (2021) linked all four elements by conceptualizing how production management can affect long-term farm income and ESs through its influence on soil health.

However, there are few studies that address the whole question with an integrated approach, and in the way presented here. Few studies link all four elements of the question, and few studies consider the large range of ESs (Dominati et al. 2019). Consequently, current literature does not include the various synergies and trade-offs that can arise among ESs, and in simultaneous relation to production management, soil health, and farm income. In addition, studies linking ESs and soil health tend to consider ESs as arbitrary benefits resulting from soil health improvement, rather than the primary objective at the centre of the question. We consider that it is crucial to maintain ESs at the centre of the question. This is because, by definition, soil health improvement is not an ultimate objective but rather a need to reach ESs improvement. In addition, ESs might play a more central role than soil health in farmers' decision making as they can be marketable to generate additional revenues.

To fill this gap, we build on previous conceptual frameworks including Kik et al. (2021), to develop an ESs-centered conceptual framework that aims to provide (1) a first integrated qualitative understanding of "how altering ESs supply simultaneously affects soil health and farm income through production management changes" and (2) a blueprint for further quantitative analysis. This framework focuses on crop production systems, and does not take into account animal husbandry.

2 | Structure and General Approach

This paper is structured to progressively explore how altering ESs supply impacts soil health and farm income through production management changes. Section 3 outlines the broader

FIGURE 1 | Context of supply and demand for ecosystem services (ESs). Farmers supply ESs while stakeholders express a demand for them which can be accompanied by incentives toward farm revenues and costs. Altering ESs supply affects production management, soil health, and consequently farm income through revenues and costs. The effect on farm income influences a farmer's decision-making regarding ESs to be supplied.

market context of ESs demand and supply. Section 4 introduces the conceptual framework, focusing on the supply side and the interactions between ESs, production management, soil health, and farm income. Section 5 integrates these components to describe how farmers might access distinct strategies to alter their ESs supply, and how distinct strategies might relate to distinct outcomes. Section 6 provides a semi-quantitative illustration of the framework's application in decision-making.

The approach to develop the materials in all sections consisted of an iterative process combining literature review, expert discussions, and narrative syntheses. Details on the methodological approach are provided in the relevant sections.

3 | Market Context: Demand and Supply for ESs

Figure 1 presents the market context of demand and supply of ESs. The demand side is represented by stakeholders interested in ESs, such as the European Union (Schulte et al. 2019), national institutions, NGOs (Schulte et al. 2019), companies (Arla Foods, n.d.; FrieslandCampina 2024), or even consumers (Latvala et al. 2021). The supply side is represented by farms.

Demand can vary over time and between stakeholders (Schulte et al. 2019), and can be accompanied by incentives (Arla Foods, n.d.) that can encourage farmers to align their supply with demand. Incentives are instruments that can be used by stakeholders to motivate farmers to enhance their supply of specific ESs. Different types of incentives exist, and they can be directed toward revenues through payments or toward costs through, for instance, rent reduction, training, or discounts on machinery (Piñeiro et al. 2020; Vanzini et al. 2024). The most well-established incentives are payment for the provisioning ESs: food, feed, and bio-based materials. However, financial incentives for other ESs also exist. Those consist, for instance, of agri-environmental schemes that national governments

and the European Union use to reward farmers for protecting ecosystems and biodiversity (Schaub et al. 2023; Schulte et al. 2019), or payments from companies, such as Arla Foods, which rewards its farmers for climate mitigation and protection of nature and biodiversity (Arla Foods, n.d.). In certain cases, groups of stakeholders cooperate to jointly incentivize the provision of ESs. For instance, public-private partnerships in Brazil organize and finance payments for ESs to farmers to preserve water quantity and quality by increasing forest cover (Zanella et al. 2014).

Based on the level of incentives offered by stakeholders, farmers may alter their ESs supply. This requires production management changes which can simultaneously also affect soil health. The changes that occur on the farm, in terms of ESs, production management, and soil health, have consequences for the farm income through changes in revenues, including financial incentives and costs.

4 | Conceptual Framework: Altering ESs Supply in Relation to Production Management, Soil Health, and Farm Income

Figure 2 presents the conceptual framework approach in which "Altering ESs" is the objective, while considering the direct and indirect influence this has on soil health, production management, and farm income. From this approach, it appears that "Altering ESs" results in a sequence of choices and consequences that create a combined effect on farm income. This sequence can be described in the following four relationships in Figure 2: (1) "Altering ESs" requires changing production management; (2) changing production management can influence soil health; (3) "Altering ESs" indirectly influences soil health through changes in production management (this does not represent the direct, mechanical linkage between soil health and ESs); (4) "Altering ESs", production management changes, and soil health changes have a combined effect on farm income.

FIGURE 2 | Conceptual framework approach to the supply of ecosystem services (ESs).

In the following sections (4.1–4.4), each relationship is explored in detail and described qualitatively. We performed a narrative review of synthesis papers to explore the relationship between ESs and production management (Section 4.1), and production management and soil health (Section 4.2). The review methods are explained in detail in the Supporting Information A-IV and follow a comparable approach to Maenhout et al. (2024). In short, the literature search was performed in Scopus and Google Scholar, and synthesis papers exploring the link between specific production management changes and ESs or soil health were collected. Synthesis papers consist of systematic and non-systematic reviews, meta-analyses, second-order meta-analyses, and so-called synthesis papers. The lists of ESs, production management changes, and soil health indicators considered in our search were based on multiple frameworks and literature sources (see Supporting Information A for detailed selection procedures and lists with definitions). The list of ESs was established based on the three main classification frameworks of ESs being CICES V5.1, MEA, and TEEB (Haines-Young and Potschin 2018; MEA 2005; TEEB 2010) and the pre-selection of ESs relevant in the agricultural context from Paul et al. (2021). Following this, we used three selection criteria to define our list of ESs: ESs can be impacted by production management changes (Criterion 1), are relevant for the general arable context (Criterion 2), and are distinct from each other (i.e., the meaning of each does not strongly coincide with another) (Criterion 3). We ended up with a list of 20 ESs including, among others, water quality, carbon sequestration, and pollination (see Supporting Information A-I).

The list of production management changes (commonly named farming practices) was first established by including the list of production management changes presented in three papers categorizing them in the context of production management, soil health, and ESs (Helming et al. 2018; Kik et al. 2021; Techen and Helming 2017). This was then presented to experts at our consortium meeting (SoilValues) in 2024, which led to some adaptations in the list. We ended up with 32 production management changes including, among others, cover crops, reduced tillage, and agroforestry. However, while all production management changes are presented separately

in all Supporting Information, some changes were grouped when presented in this paper. For instance, compost, manure, slurry, and biochar were grouped into a single production management change when presented in the paper. Therefore, only 21 production management changes are presented here (see Supporting Information A-II).

The list of soil health indicators was first established based on four papers providing lists of soil health indicators in the context of production management, ESs, and farm income (Adhikari and Hartemink 2016; Arshad and Martin 2002; Kik et al. 2021; Stevens 2018). Following this, we used three selection criteria: soil health indicators have to be manageable (Criterion 1), are distinct from each other (i.e., the meaning of each does not strongly coincide with another) (Criterion 2), and are not rarely used (Criterion 3). Finally, we discussed our pre-selection with two experienced soil scientists and updated our list. We ended up with 18 soil health indicators including, among others, bulk density, pH, and cation exchange capacity (see Supporting Information A-III).

Based on the review of synthesis papers, we described how ESs are affected by various production management changes (Table 1) and the effect of these changes on soil health indicators (Table 2). Preliminary tables were reviewed by five experts and, based on their feedback, extended with additional literature. In total, we collected 49 reviews, 28 meta-analyses, and 3 second-order meta-analyses.

4.1 | How Altering ESs Supply Requires Production Management Changes

Altering ESs supply requires production management changes. Table 1 presents this relation by showing how 20 ESs can be affected by 21 production management changes (detailed version with references in Supporting Information C).

In many cases, one single ES or a bundle of ESs can be enhanced by several production management changes. For instance, water quality can be improved through agroforestry, field margins,

TABLE 1 | How ecosystem services (ESS) are affected by various production management changes based on the review of synthesis papers.

Categories	Ecosystem services																			
	Provisioning			Regulating						Supporting						Cultural				
Production management decisions	Cultivated plants	Blue water	Waste filtration	Waste decomposition	Erosion control	Flood control	Fire protection	Pollination	Pest & disease control	Water quality	Local climate reg.	Global climate reg.	Carbon seq.	Non-CO2 GHG reg.	Habitat	Biodiversity	NUE	Green water	Activities	Culture & heritage
Strategic soil management	Reduce machine weight and stress on soil	☆				☆				☆				☆				☆		
	Subsoil management	☆	☆			☆		☆	☆	☆			☆	☆				☆		
Land use	Agroforestry	☆☆	☆			☆☆		☆☆	☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Field margins	☆☆		☆		☆☆		☆☆	☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Intercropping	☆☆		☆		☆☆		☆☆	☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Legumes	☆☆				☆☆		☆☆	☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Use crop rotation	☆☆				☆☆		☆☆	☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Include cover crop	☆☆	☆			☆☆		☆☆	☆☆	☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
Crop management	Retain crop residue	☆☆				☆☆		☆☆	☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Incorporate residues in the soil	☆				☆				☆			☆	☆			☆	☆		
	Decrease fertilizer use	☆☆				☆☆				☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		
	Fertilizer timing and placement	☆☆				☆☆				☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		
	Biotic inoculation	☆				☆				☆			☆	☆			☆	☆		
	Alternative pesticide management	☆				☆				☆			☆	☆			☆	☆		
Tactical soil management	Decrease irrigation	☆☆				☆☆				☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Improve drainage	☆☆		☆		☆☆				☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Include land terracing	☆☆		☆		☆☆				☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Use of lime & gypsum	☆☆		☆		☆☆				☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Mulching	☆☆	☆			☆☆				☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆
	Organic amendments application	☆☆	☆	☆	☆	☆☆				☆☆			☆☆	☆☆			☆☆	☆☆		☆☆

Note: Each cell color indicates the effect of a production management change (row) on an ES (column) based on one or several synthesis papers. When several synthesis papers were collected for a single cell, the reported effect in that cell was calculated by combining findings from all its synthesis papers (see Supporting Information A-IV). Effects are described qualitatively as five levels: Dark green: Positive effect; Light green: Neutral to positive effect; Orange: Neutral/unclear effect; Light red: Neutral to negative; Dark red: Negative. The stars indicate the evidence level supporting the reported effect, from low evidence (empty star) to high evidence (three stars). Abbreviations: Carbon seq., carbon sequestration; NUE, nutrient use efficiency; Reg, regulation.

TABLE 2 | The effect of production management changes on soil health indicators based on the review of synthesis papers.

Categories	Soil health indicators																			
	Physical								Chemical								Biological			
	Aggr. size	Aggr. stability	Bulk density	AWC	Infiltration	CEC	pH	Salinity	Tot. N	Tot. P	Available N	Available P	Pollutants	SOM /SOC	Fungi	Bacteria	Nematodes	Earthworms		
Strategic soil management			★		☆													☆		
Reduce machine weight and stress on soil			★		☆															
Subsoil management			★	★	★						★	★		★	★	★	★	★		
Reduce tillage	★	★	★	★	★	★	★							★	★	★	★	★		
Agroforestry	★	★												★	★	★	★	★		
Field margins																				
Intercropping																				
Legumes		★	★	★	★										★	★	★	★		
Use crop rotation		★	★	★	★		★								★	★	★	★		
Include cover crop		★	★	★	★		★								★	★	★	★		
Retain crop residue	★	★	★	★	★	★	★													
Incorporate residues in the soil		★		★		★	★		★											
Decrease fertilizer use	★	★	★				★													
Fertilizer timing and placement																				
Crop management																				
Biotic inoculation																				
Alternative pesticide management																				
Decrease irrigation							★													
Improve drainage																				
Include land terracing																				
Use of lime & gypsum		★						★												
Mulching		★	★																	
Organic amendments application		★	★	★	★	★	★	★	★	★	★	★	★	★	★	★	★	★		

Note: Each cell color indicates the effect of a production management change (row) on a soil health indicator (column) based on one or several synthesis papers. When several synthesis papers were collected for a single cell, the reported effect in that cell was calculated by combining findings from all its synthesis papers (see Supporting Information A-IV). Effects are described qualitatively at 5 levels: Dark green: Positive effect; Light green: Neutral to positive effect; Orange: Neutral/unclear effect; Light red: Neutral to negative; Dark red: Negative. The number of stars indicates the evidence level supporting the reported effect, from low (empty star) to high evidence (3 stars). Abbreviations: Aggr., aggregate; AWC, available water capacity; Tot., total.

fertilizer placement, and decreasing fertilizer rate, while carbon sequestration can also be enhanced through agroforestry and cover crops but not through fertilizer placement and decreasing fertilizer rate. This indicates that if a farmer is willing to improve one single ES or a bundle of ESs, they can choose between several production management changes. For instance, if one wants to enhance water quality, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity, one can implement agroforestry, cover crops, or intercropping (Table 1).

Depending on the exact production management changes selected to enhance the ESs initially targeted, synergies and trade-offs could arise with other ESs, as many, if not all, production management changes affect multiple ESs. For instance, using the above example, if one wants to enhance water quality, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity, one might opt for cover crops or intercropping, but depending on the choice other ESs will be affected differently. Cover crops, but not intercropping, could enhance erosion control and flood control (synergies) but decrease blue and green water (trade-offs) (Table 1).

While Table 1 represents a good starting point for discussion and further analysis, a more detailed approach is necessary when addressing problems in practice. First, multiple environmental cofactors, such as the climate and inherent soil properties, can influence the results (Jeffery et al. 2017; Wang et al. 2021). For instance, the meta-analysis of Jeffery et al. (2017) showed a positive effect of biochar on cultivated plants in tropical climates but a negative impact in temperate climates. Second, experimental cofactors such as sampling depth (Palm et al. 2014) and experimental duration can influence the results. Third, more specific production management changes than the ones defined in our framework may have to be taken into account. For instance, “cover crops” encompasses many types of cover crops, among which some are legumes and some are not. While Quemada et al. (2013) showed that cover crops do not affect cultivated plants when considering them as one category, they showed that legume cover crops have a significant positive impact on cultivated plants while non-legume cover crops have a negative non-significant impact.

4.2 | How Production Management Changes Affect Soil Health

The impact of 21 production management changes on the 18 soil health indicators we reviewed is shown in Table 2 (more detailed version with references in Supporting Information C). While some of these relationships have been studied more extensively, such as those related to soil organic matter/carbon (SOM/SOC) or tillage practices, others, such as those related to subsoil management and machine weight, have remained understudied.

In many cases, one single soil health indicator or a bundle of soil health indicators can be enhanced by several production management changes. For instance, many production management changes, including cover crops, less crop residue removal, and organic amendments, can contribute to increasing SOM/SOC.

Consequently, when considering improving specific soil health indicators, one may have several options for modifying production management.

While specific soil health indicators may be enhanced by various production management changes, different changes may lead to distinct trade-offs and synergies among soil health indicators. For instance, if one considers increasing earthworm abundance and diversity, one may choose between no tillage and increasing organic amendments. While no tillage could increase bulk density and have a limited effect on bacterial abundance and diversity, an increase in organic amendments could decrease bulk density and increase bacterial abundance and diversity.

4.3 | How Altering ESs Supply Affects Soil Health Through Production Management Changes

Because ESs supply can be altered by various production management changes, and production management changes can affect soil health indicators in various ways, altering ESs supply can have various effects on soil health indicators (Figure 3). This can result in a synergy or trade-off between ESs supply and soil health, depending on whether the change in soil health is considered beneficial or detrimental, which is context-specific.

Even when aiming at the same specific ES, synergies and trade-offs with soil health indicators might differ. For instance, when attempting to enhance water quality, one might decide to plant cover crops or decrease fertilizer rate, but the impact of both changes on soil health indicators will differ. Indeed, it could be expected that cover crops increase SOM/SOC, earthworm abundance and diversity, and infiltration rate among other indicators, while decreasing fertilizer rate might reduce SOM/SOC without affecting earthworm abundance and diversity and infiltration rate (Figure 3).

Additionally, it is important to note that, through production management, altering both soil ESs and non-soil ESs can affect soil health. For instance, enhancing pollination (non-soil ESs) can result in planting cover crops and, consequently, positively impact SOM/SOC and other soil health indicators (Figure 3).

4.4 | How Altering ESs Supply Affects Farm Income

To put the previous sections into an economic perspective, this section (1) defines farm income in the context of altering ESs supply, and (2) describes qualitatively how altering ESs supply can impact farm income through changes in ESs supply, production management, and soil health.

With farm income we always refer to the net farm income (FI), defined as the difference between the revenues and costs (C) of a farm (Kay et al. 2012). The revenues can be sub-divided into crop yield revenues (R_Y) and revenues from other ESs (R_{ESs}):

$$FI = R_Y + R_{ESs} - C \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 3 | How altering ecosystem services (ESs) supply affects soil health indicators through changes in production management. Black arrow = “This ES can be enhanced through this production management change”; Green arrow = “The production management change increases the soil health indicator”; Red arrow = “The production management change decreases the soil health indicator”. SOM/SOC = Soil organic matter/Soil organic carbon. Please be aware that an increase/decrease does not necessarily correspond to a beneficial/detrimental effect. For illustration purposes, we use a limited set of ESs, production management changes, and soil health indicators.

Crop yield revenues (R_Y) refer to the revenues that are generated from the yield of crops and can be defined as:

$$R_Y = \sum_{j=1}^J Y_j \times P_j \quad (2)$$

where J represents the different crops within the cropping plan, and Y_j is a continuous variable referring to the yield of each crop J . Each Y_j represents a specific ES, and a subcategory to the ES “Cultivated plants” in Table 1. P_j is a fixed parameter referring to the price of each crop J .

Revenues from other ESs (R_{ESs}) refer to the revenues that are generated from other ESs than crop yields and can be defined as:

$$R_{ESs} = \sum_{e=1}^E ES_e \times P_e \quad (3)$$

where E represents different ESs, ES_e is a continuous variable defined as the intensity of supply of each ecosystem service E . P_e is a fixed parameter referring to the price of each ecosystem service E . For simplicity, revenues from other ESs are further referred to as ES revenues.

Costs (C) can be defined as:

$$C = \sum_{pm=1}^{PM} (M_{pm} \times C_{pm}) \quad (4)$$

where PM represents different production management decisions. M_{pm} is a binary or continuous variable indicating the use of a production management decision pm (when binary), or the intensity of the production management decision pm (when continuous). C_{pm} is the cost incurred for using a certain production management decision pm . For reasons of simplicity, we do not distinguish between variable and fixed costs and

consider that costs solely depend on the production management applied, including its intensity.

When a farmer decides to alter ESs supply through a change in production management, this can affect crop yield revenues, other ESs revenues, and costs, resulting in either a positive or negative net impact on farm income (relations 4.1–4.3 in Figure 2). First, altering ESs supply can affect crop yield revenues positively or negatively depending on the effect of the selected farm practice(s) on Y_j . This corresponds to relation 4.1 in Figure 2 as Y_j is a subcategory of the ES “Cultivated plants”. The change in Y_j might occur through a change in the cropping plan and/or a direct effect on yield. Indeed, as shown in Table 1, some farm practices affecting ESs supply lead to a change in cropping plan (e.g., intercropping, agroforestry) and/or can directly affect “Cultivated plants” positively (e.g., mulching) or negatively (e.g., decreasing fertilizer rate). Second, altering ESs supply is expected to increase ESs revenues (relation 4.1) as one or more ESs are expected to be improved (Table 1). This holds as long as there is a payment for the improved ESs. However, trade-offs between ESs (Table 1) could potentially result in a net negative effect on ESs revenues. Third, the required changes in production management (Table 1) to alter ESs supply can increase (e.g., cover crops) or decrease (e.g., reduce fertilizer use) costs (relation 4.2). Finally, because soil health is key for long-term productivity (Kik et al. 2021), the effect on soil health can affect the long-term effect on Y_j , and consequently affect crop yield revenues (relation 4.3). As a consequence of the various effects that altering ESs supply can have on crop yield revenues, ESs revenues, and costs, as well as the combined effect of altering ESs supply on farm income can either be positive or negative, which partly depends on the time horizon the farmer takes into account.

5 | How Altering ESs Supply Affects Soil Health, and Farm Income: Various Strategies With Distinct Implications

Here, we integrate all relations from Section 4 to describe how altering ESs supply can simultaneously affect soil health and farm

income through production management changes. We show that (1) there are various strategies available to farmers to alter ESs supply while integrating soil health and farm income in decision-making, and (2) distinct strategies can require distinct production management changes which (3) can result in distinct outcomes. Distinct outcomes can differ in terms of effects on farm income, need for ESs revenues to preserve farm income, and potential for ESs and soil health improvement. We assume that farmers aim to maximize profit (though his assumption does not mean that they actually reach maximal profit).

We identified three strategies: “Cost reduction”, “Revenue increase”, and “ESs focus” (Figure 4). Each leads to two to four possible outcomes that differ in terms of effect on farm income, need for ESs revenues to ensure farm income improvement, and potential for ESs and soil health improvement.

A farmer following the “cost reduction” strategy aims to alter ESs supply by changing production management so that the costs of production management decrease more than any potential reduction in crop yield revenues. By definition, when undertaking this strategy, one does not especially aim to enhance ESs that are marketed. This can occur, for instance, by increasing input efficiency and consequently reducing fertilizer rate, pesticide rate, or irrigation. If this strategy is taken, it will improve farm income whether or not additional payments are received for ESs revenues (respectively outcome CR.2 and CR.1). Therefore, this strategy does not incur any need for additional payments for ESs revenues to ensure a farm income improvement. Still, if other factors than farm income limit the farmer’s willingness to alter ESs supply, it might be necessary to incentivize the farmer with additional payments for ESs revenues (CR.2).

A farmer following the “revenue increase” strategy aims to alter ESs supply by increasing the net total revenue of the farm. This can occur by increasing crop yield revenues and ESs revenues. By definition, when undertaking this strategy, one aims to enhance specific ESs that are marketed, being crop yield for crop yield revenues, or other ES(s) for ESs revenues. As shown in Table 1, several production management changes can increase yield (e.g., mulching) and might consequently increase crop yield revenues. Other production management changes have considerable positive effects on ESs (e.g., cover crops) and might therefore have a high potential to increase ESs revenues. This strategy might improve farm income, with or without the need for additional payments for ESs revenues, depending on the relative effect on crop yield revenues and costs. On the one hand, if crop yield revenues increase more than any potential increase in costs, farm income would always be improved whether or not additional payments are received for ESs revenues (respectively outcome RI.1 and RI.2). On the other hand, if crop yield revenues do not increase or not as much as the costs, this strategy would lead to a detrimental outcome for farm income (RI.3) without additional payments for ESs revenues (RI.4).

A farmer following the “ESs focus” strategy aims to alter ESs supply by sacrificing crop yield revenues in favour of higher ESs revenues, which by definition will be derived from ESs other than crop yield. In this strategy, crop yield revenues decline more than any potential reduction in costs (the opposite would

characterize the “cost reduction” strategy). For simplicity, we assume here that costs remain unchanged. This strategy could be realized, for instance, by implementing large field margins or retaining more crop residues. Farm income would only be preserved if ESs revenues increase at least as much as the decrease in crop yield revenues (EF.2).

While the different strategies yield different effects on farm income and have different levels of reliance on ESs revenues, their potential to enhance ESs supply and soil health might also differ. Here, we hypothesize that the outcomes that do not require payment for ESs revenues to ensure farm income improvement (i.e., CR.1, CR.2, RI.1, RI.2) tend to have a less potential to improve ESs supply and soil health than the outcomes that do require payments for ESs revenues (i.e., RI.3, RI.4, EF.1, EF.2). This is because, assuming that farmers are profit maximizers, there would be little possibility for them to further improve their farm income without additional payment for ESs revenues, and consequently very limited possibilities to enhance ESs supply and soil health through CR.1, CR.2, RI.1, or RI.2.

Figure 4 can serve as a guiding process to support farmers’ decision-making when aiming to alter ESs supply while integrating soil health and farm income in decision-making. It can inform them about what they should consider to reach that aim.

1. What is the specific aim? For instance, do they want to alter ESs in general, or enhance particular ESs; and if they want to improve or simply preserve soil health and farm income?
2. Which strategies are they willing to undertake to reach this aim? Different farmers’ profiles might be more inclined toward certain strategies. For instance, instead of aiming to maximize profit, some farmers may prefer to reduce profit variability over time.
3. Which production management changes are required? And if no production management changes are possible, how will aim and strategy be adapted (feedback loop to (1) and (2))?
4. What might be the outcomes in terms of (a) the effect on farm income, (b) the need for additional payments for ESs revenues, and (c) the potential to enhance ESs supply and soil health? This might feed back into the aim, strategy, and production management changes, or might indicate a need to negotiate with stakeholders to increase the price of certain ESs.

Which strategies and outcomes are available to a farmer will depend on the baseline production management and soil health, as well as the local soil and environmental conditions. This is illustrated as part of our framework illustration in the next section.

6 | How to Alter ESs Supply While Integrating Soil Health and Farm Income in Decision Making: Framework Illustration

We illustrate the framework by using data from two standard farms with an area of 100 ha in The Netherlands (Kik, Claassen,

FIGURE 4 | Schematic overview of (a) strategies that farmers can adopt when aiming to alter ESs supply while integrating soil health and farm income in decision-making, (b) possible production management changes required by each strategy, and (c) possible outcomes resulting from each strategy. Each strategy may lead to multiple outcomes, with each outcome being labeled using the initials of its related strategy and a number to distinguish among them (e.g., CR.1 = outcome “Cost reduction 1”; CR.2 = outcome “Cost reduction 2”; RI.1 = outcome “Revenue increase 1”; EF.1 = outcome “ESs focus 1”).

Ros, et al. 2024), an intensive and an extensive farm on clay soil (see description in Table 3). The illustration shows (1) how the framework can assist farmers’ decision-making; and (2) how different farms may achieve distinct outcomes when aiming to alter ESs supply while integrating soil health and farm income in their decision-making. In this illustration, we assume that both farms aim for altering ESs supply in general without targeting specific ESs.

In Table 3, we present a summary of each farm’s baseline production management and performance on soil health indicators. The clay intensive farm has a more intensive production management with a more intensive crop rotation than the clay extensive farm, and fewer production management decisions beneficial for ESs. For instance, it cultivates cover crops half as frequently and sells crop residues (cereal straw), while the clay extensive farm retains them. Due to their differing baseline production management, both farms have distinct farm incomes and performances on soil health indicators. The clay intensive farm has a higher farm income, but its soil organic matter (SOM)

input is insufficient to preserve soil health in the long term, while the clay extensive farm has no specific soil health issue.

Because both farms differ in baseline production management and performance on soil health indicators (Table 3), their available options to alter ESs supply while integrating soil health in decision-making diverge (Table 4). Because the clay intensive farm applies fewer production management decisions beneficial for ESs it has initially more available options to alter ESs supply. However, when considering performance on soil health indicators, the options to alter ESs would be reduced for the clay intensive farm but not the clay extensive farm, because only the clay intensive farm has a specific soil health issue.

When ignoring soil health, both farms can access the “cost reduction” strategy by decreasing their fertilizer application (Table 5). We consider a decrease in N fertilizer that would not affect the yield (i.e., a 50% decrease in the difference between N advice and N available for crop growth in each farm, see Table 7 of Kik, Claassen, Ros, et al. 2024). By following this strategy, both farms

TABLE 3 | Summary of baseline production management, farm income, and performance on soil health indicators at clay-intensive and clay-extensive farms.

Years	Farms overview															
	Clay intensive								Clay extensive							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Crop rotation	WP	WW	SO	SB	WP	WW	CA	SB	WP	WW	SB	WW	WP	WW	SB	WW
Cover crops		CC				CC			CC			CC		CC		CC
Crop residues		S				S			K			K		K		K
N fertilizer applied					110 kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹								130 kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹			
Crop yield revenues					6.281 € ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹								4.522 € ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹			
Costs					5.634 € ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹								4.097 € ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹			
Farm income					647 € ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹								425 € ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹			
Soil health	Low soil organic matter (SOM)								No specific soil quality issue							

Abbreviations: CA, carrots; CC, cover crop; K, keep crop residues; S, sell crop residues; SB, sugar beets; SC, silage corn; SO, seed onions; WB, winter barley; WP, ware potatoes; WW, winter wheat. [Correction added on 6 September 2025, after first online publication: In Table 3, the top heading has been updated to “Farms overview” in this version.]

TABLE 4 | Available options to alter ecosystem services (ESs) supply for both farms while (a) ignoring, or (b) integrating soil health as part of the decision-making process.

Options to alter Ess	Ignoring soil health		Integrating soil health	
	Clay intensive	Clay extensive	Clay intensive	Clay extensive
Decrease fertilizer	✓	✓	✗	✓
Cover crop	✓	✗	✓	✗
Retain residues	✓	✗	✓	✗

are expected to see an improvement in four ESs (Water quality, Non-CO₂ GHG regulation, Biodiversity, and NUE) and in farm income. While this strategy would allow the clay extensive farm to preserve its soil health, it does not give the clay intensive farm the opportunity to simultaneously preserve its soil health. Therefore, when integrating soil health in decision-making, this farm might rather consider other alternative strategies. The clay intensive farm could consider accessing the “revenue increase” strategy by cultivating more cover crops, or the “ESs focus” strategy by retaining crop residues. Those strategies would help the farm to preserve a larger amount of ESs and its soil health, but would have a detrimental effect on farm income in the absence of additional payments for ESs revenues (Table 5). Consequently, the clay intensive farm might be reluctant to adopt those strategies, and therefore, to preserve its soil health.

In this illustration, we assumed that both farms aim for improved ESs supply in general without targeting specific ESs. However, targeting specific ESs could modify and limit access

to the different strategies and possible outcomes. In addition, the interpretation of the different outcomes could be affected as improving fewer but targeted ESs might be preferred over improving more but nontargeted ESs. Therefore, it would be relevant to address stakeholders' demand for specific ESs in future analysis.

7 | Discussion

7.1 | General

The main aim of this conceptual framework was to provide a qualitative understanding of how altering ESs supply simultaneously affects soil health and farm income through production management changes while considering each component's complexity.

Although previous studies have provided a basis to answer this question by linking elements of this question (e.g., Kik

TABLE 5 | Strategies and possible outcomes for both farms to enhance ecosystem services (ESS) supply while integrating soil health and farm income in decision-making.

Farm	Clay intensive			Clay extensive		
	Strategies	Costs reduction ↘ fertilizer	Revenue increase Cover crops	R_ESs focus Retain residues	Costs reduction ↘ fertilizer	Others No option
Outcomes	Baseline	CR.1 or CR.2 (R_ESs ≥ 0)	RI.3 or RI.4 (R_ESs ≥ 75)	EF.1 or EF.2 (R_ESs ≥ 75)	Baseline	CR.1 or CR.2 (R_ESs ≥ 0)
Crop yield revenues	6,281 €	6,281 €	6,281 €	6,206 €	4,522 €	4,522 €
Costs	5,634 €	5,579 €	5,709 €	5,634 €	4,097 €	4,055 €
Farm income (without ESS revenues)	647 €	702 €	572 €	572 €	425 €	468 €
ESS revenues required	—	NO	YES ≥ 75 €	YES ≥ 75 €	—	NO
Soil health preserved	X	X	✓	✓	✓	✓
ESS improvement	—	Water quality Non-CO ₂ GHG reg.	Cultivated plants Erosion control Flood control Pollination Pest control	Cultivated plants Erosion control Flood control Water quality Global climate reg.	—	Water quality Non-CO ₂ GHG reg.
		Biodiversity NUE	Water quality Carbon seq. Habitat Biodiversity	Carbon seq. NUE Green water		Biodiversity NUE
ESS deterioration	—	—	Blue water Green water	Non-CO ₂ GHG reg.	—	—

Note: Values are given in € ha⁻¹ y⁻¹. Legend: CR. 1 = outcome “Cost reduction 1”; R1.3 = outcome “Revenue increase 3”; EF.1 = outcome “Ess focus 1”. [Correction added on 6 September 2025, after first online publication: In Table 5, the values of the Outcomes have been realigned in this version.]

et al. 2021; Stevens 2018), they only fragmentarily addressed this issue and usually considered a small number of ESs (Dominati et al. 2019).

To fill this gap, this conceptual framework is built on Kik et al. (2021) to consider ESs more holistically and at the center of decision-making. We did this by setting ESs at the center of the conceptual approach (Section 4), and by including a broad set of ESs (Section 4.1) and soil health indicators (Section 4.2).

7.2 | Key Insights Derived From the Framework

The conceptual framework provides six key insights on the research question.

First, altering ESs supply results in a sequence of choices and consequences that affect together ESs supply, soil health, and farm income. This was caused by setting ESs at the centre of our conceptual approach and then exploring the relation between ESs supply, production management, soil health, and farm income. It was shown that altering ESs supply requires making choices in terms of ESs to be improved and production management changes, which results in consequences for ESs supply itself, soil health, and farm income. For instance, improving water quality requires production management changes such as increasing crop residue retention (Table 1), which can improve soil health indicators (SOM, infiltration, etc.) but reduce farm income if no additional revenues for ESs are obtained.

Second, the framework revealed synergies and trade-offs that can arise between a broad range of ESs when modifying production management. We build on previous literature exploring those relations (Beillouin et al. 2021; Maenhout et al. 2024; Tamburini et al. 2020) with a broad range of ESs and production management changes based on a clear selection procedure.

Third, the framework revealed synergies and trade-offs between a broad range of soil health indicators when modifying production management. This conceptual framework contributes to the current literature exploring the relation between production management and soil health (Bai et al. 2018; Li et al. 2019; Sandén et al. 2018) by considering 18 soil health indicators in relation to a wide variety of production management changes.

Fourth, we shed light on the indirect relation between altering ESs supply and soil health. We revealed that distinct choices in ESs to be altered and production management changes lead to distinct synergies and trade-offs between ESs and soil health indicators. To our knowledge, this is the first concept that clearly describes this, expanding existing literature that describes the direct linkage between soil and ESs (e.g., Adhikari and Hartemink 2016; Dominati et al. 2010; Schwilch et al. 2016).

Fifth, our framework shows how altering ESs supply directly and indirectly affects farm income through changes in ESs supply, soil health, and production management (Section 4.4). To our knowledge, this is the first conceptual framework that describes how making decisions regarding ESs supply can affect

farm income through simultaneous changes in ESs supply, soil health, and production management.

Finally, combining all insights, it becomes clear that altering ESs supply can affect ESs themselves, soil health, and farm income in various ways, depending on a farmer's choices, baseline production management, and performance on soil health indicators (Sections 5 and 6). Making our framework more concrete in terms of quantification could help farmers to make decisions in agreement with their choices in the light of their long-term farm, ESs, and soil strategy.

7.3 | Reflection on Incentives for ESs Revenues

In this conceptual framework, we consider that incentives for ESs revenues should be provided to farmers when they incur income loss through altering their ESs supply. This brings two reflection points.

First, incentivizing farmers to adopt changes beneficial for ESs supply would favour farmers that currently have the most unsustainable production management. As shown in Section 6, farmers with unsustainable production management could have more opportunities than other farmers to enhance their ESs supply and get access to incentives for ESs revenues. Such mechanisms might be considered unfair by farmers with more sustainable production management.

Second, such incentives might be irrelevant to motivate farmers as it could be in their self-interest to adopt production management changes beneficial for ESs, even if their farm income is initially reduced. This is because adopting more sustainable production management can be accompanied by soil health improvement, which can serve functional objectives from the farm itself (Schulte et al. 2019) and enhance long-term farm income (Kik et al. 2021). As a consequence, the need for additional incentives might be less than expected and could be mitigated by increasing farmers' awareness of the benefits of ESs and soil health for their interest. This is because behavioral characteristics of farmers, such as their awareness, can influence their decision making (Bartkowski and Bartke 2018). Thus, it is key to raise that awareness.

7.4 | Implications

The conceptual framework has three implications to support farmers and stakeholders' decision-making when aiming to alter ESs supply while integrating soil health and farm income in decision-making.

First, altering ESs supply while integrating soil health and farm income in decision-making might require different decisions across farms, for both farmers and stakeholders. Different farmers might need to make different production management changes as the set of potential changes can vary across farms. The set of potential changes depends on a farmer's specific aims in terms of ESs, soil health and farm income, the availability of additional revenues for ESs, and the baseline

production management and performance on soil health indicators (Sections 5 and 6). Because farmers may need to make different production management changes, their needs for additional ESs revenues might differ. Consequently, stakeholders' requirements to provide additional ESs revenues may vary across farms (Sections 5 and 6).

Second, Section 5 can serve as a guiding process for farmers and stakeholders to enhance ESs supply while integrating soil health and farm income in decision-making. For farmers, the guiding process supports them in identifying relevant production management changes for enhancing ESs supply and assessing their synergies and trade-offs with soil health and farm income in the light of their strategic choices. Because the guiding process can also support identifying if additional revenues for ESs are needed to preserve farm income, it can help stakeholders in determining how much additional revenues for ESs will be required to provide to farmers.

Third, Tables 1 and 2 provide reflection tools for farmers and stakeholders to identify potential production management changes beneficial for ESs supply and soil health. Because what is shown in both tables is not context-specific, we advise using them as a reflection tool in combination with detailed Tables 1 and 2 (Supporting Information C and D), as well as farmers' and stakeholders' know-how (tacit knowledge).

In addition, this conceptual framework suggests a shift in focus from the current soil health approach, which tends to focus on improving soil health while considering ESs in limited numbers and only as resulting from soil health improvement (e.g., Kik et al. 2021). We argue that setting ESs as the main objective at the centre of the problem could have a more attractive appeal to farmers for improving soil health. This is because it might facilitate the simultaneous improvement of soil health and farm income as ESs could generate additional revenues by being marketed. We expect this approach to offer more opportunities to generate additional ESs revenues as it allows targeting specific ESs that might be marketable among a broad set of ESs and makes the improvement tangible to a wide group of stakeholders.

7.5 | Next Steps: A Basis for Deeper Quantitative Analysis

This conceptual framework provided valuable insights, but deeper quantitative analyses are necessary to provide clearer answers to this question, which can support the transition toward farming systems associated with better ESs supply, soil health, and farm income. Quantitative analyses are required to provide quantitative answers such as the quantitative effect on farm income when altering ESs supply. This could support farmers and stakeholders to negotiate prices of ESs supplied. In addition, deeper analyses are needed to take into account the farm context, which can, for instance, influence the effect of production management on ESs and soil health indicators (Jeffery et al. 2017; Wang et al. 2021; Young et al. 2021). While our conceptual framework provided a good overview of synergies and trade-offs, it did not account for context.

Bio-economic farm models offer the possibility for quantitative analysis and to evaluate synergies and trade-offs between

various farm aspects (Schreefel et al. 2022). In addition, they can be developed to account for context specificity (Kik, Claassen, Ros, et al. 2024). While there already exist many bio-economic farm models (Groot et al. 2012; Janssen and van Ittersum 2007), current models fail to include all the necessary elements tackled in this study. For instance, the model of Kik, Claassen, Ros, et al. (2024), used in a Dutch case study (Kik, Claassen, Meuwissen, et al. 2024), links production management, farm income, and soil health, but ignores ESs supply.

The conceptual framework can serve as a basis to extend existing bio-economic farm model(s) in various ways. The list of ESs and soil health indicators in Sections 4.1 and 4.2 can support the selection of ESs and soil health indicators, and Tables 1 and 2 could be implemented in a model as a starting point to link production management changes to ESs supply and soil health respectively. Therefore, the results from this conceptual framework can serve as a blueprint for deeper quantitative analysis, and further on as a basis to transition toward farming systems associated with better ESs supply, soil health, and farm income.

8 | Conclusions

This conceptual framework provides key insights for an integrated understanding of how altering ESs supply simultaneously affects soil health and farm income through production management changes. This was achieved by placing ESs supply at the centre of decision-making while considering a broad range of ESs and soil health indicators. Altering ESs supply requires production management changes and affects soil health and farm income. Our framework revealed the various synergies and trade-offs that can arise among ESs and in relation to soil health and farm income when altering ESs supply. It outlined the range of possible outcomes for farmers aiming to alter ESs supply in light of specific decisions and contexts.

The insights came with implications for farmers and stakeholders, including the fact that additional incentives for ESs revenues are not always necessary. In addition, the proposed framework suggested a shift in focus that could be more appealing to farmers to improve soil health itself. Finally, we discussed the need for deeper quantitative analysis, such as bio-economic farm models, and the potential of the framework to serve as a blueprint for those models.

Author Contributions

Y. C. Wang-Touri: conceptualization, writing – original draft. **M. C. Kik:** writing – review and editing. **M. P. M. Meuwissen:** writing – review and editing. **A. B. Smit:** writing – review and editing. **H. W. Saatkamp:** conceptualization, supervision, writing – review and editing.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Supporting Information A.** Main supplementary material. **Supporting Information B.** Detailed selection of ecosystem services and soil health indicators. **Supporting Information C.** Detailed Tables 1 and 2. **Supporting Information D.** List of references used in Tables 1 and 2.